

RECLAIMING THE PAST, SHAPING THE FUTURE: CULTURAL CLUBS AND OPOBO KINGDOM'S CULTURAL GROWTH

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Abstract: Cultural clubs, like other social organizations, have emerged as significant agents of community development by mobilizing local talents, skills, and collective identities to stimulate positive change. Through organized cultural performances, festivals, language promotion, and heritage education, these clubs contribute to the preservation and transmission of indigenous traditions while strengthening social cohesion. Beyond cultural conservation, cultural clubs foster networks and partnerships that enhance economic activities such as tourism, creative industries, and small-scale enterprises within host communities. This paper examines how cultural clubs function as catalysts for cultural revitalization and socio-economic development, highlighting their role in promoting community participation, identity formation, and sustainable development. The study underscores the importance of supporting cultural clubs as strategic stakeholders in grassroots development planning.

Keywords: Cultural clubs; Community development; Cultural heritage; Social cohesion; Socio-economic revitalization

Introduction

Cultural clubs, much like other social organizations, have established themselves as vital partners in community development initiatives. They have showcased talents and skills that have driven positive transformations within their communities, playing pivotal roles in preserving cultural heritage and fostering relationships and networks that rejuvenate local socio-economic activities. Social clubs are organized groups that unite individuals with shared interests for the purposes of socializing and recreation. These clubs emerged as prominent facets of urban life with the rise of the middle class in the country, becoming essential spaces for nurturing community bonds, encouraging cultural exchange, and promoting social engagement. They mirrored the evolving social landscape of the time and reflected

the aspirations of a growing middle class seeking to define its identity and societal role. Membership in such clubs often signalled one's social status, with some evolving into exclusive circles that imposed barriers based on wealth, status, or ethnicity.

Cultural clubs, in particular, are often shaped by ethnic boundaries, as they are fundamentally designed to promote and preserve the heritage of specific ethnic groups through events, festivals, and performances. These activities provide a sense of belonging and communal identity by celebrating shared traditions and values. In doing so, they foster a deep sense of solidarity and brotherhood that inspires community awareness, encourages volunteerism, and facilitates active participation in local development efforts.

cultural heritage of the kingdom during their active

In the Opobo Kingdom, cultural associations have long been integral to the community's identity, dating back to the kingdom's founding. Noteworthy among these are the Owuogbo, Peri Ogbo, Ekina, and Orukoro (also known as Owuamapu) associations (Oko-Jaja, 2020). These cultural associations played a vital role in preserving and sustaining the rich years, while also contributing in various ways to the development of the region. Today, with the exception of the Owuogbo Society, most of these pioneering cultural groups have become moribund, if not entirely erased by the sweeping forces of Christianity and modernity. Unlike other associations, membership in the Owuogbo Society is not open to every Opobo male child; it is based on appointment by the elders of a war canoe house that has been granted a masquerade by the Owuogbo. These masquerades are showcased annually during the kingdom's Owuogbo masquerade festival. Those appointed by their respective war canoe houses form the membership of the society, which is led by the Owuogbosibidagbo, a representative from the Jungo-Manilla War Canoe houses, and supervised by the Amanyanabo (King) of the kingdom. (Andrew-Jaja, 2025).

With the advent of colonialism and the subsequent introduction of Western education and the British economic system in Africa, particularly Nigeria, a new class of educated elites emerged, gradually replacing the palm produce merchants as key players in community development. This shift sparked a wave of rural-to-urban migration, as members of the educated class moved to urban centers in search of employment within colonial companies, institutions, and other establishments. In these cities, the educated working class, which formed the nucleus of the emerging middle class, began organizing kinship and

tribal unions. These associations not only deepened their sense of duty to their native communities but also heightened their awareness of the stark contrast between their improved urban lifestyles and the persistent poverty in their rural homelands, fueling a strong commitment to initiate and support development programmes back home (Coleman, 1986, 213214).

In Opobo, one of the earliest forms of such unions included the Opobo League and the Opobo Improvement Union. These associations were established in urban centers by members of the Opobo middle class, and they played a pivotal role in awakening their members' awareness of events back home and the pressing need to contribute to the kingdom's development. Through their efforts, both the unions and their members significantly advanced the cause of communal progress. Notably, these associations laid the foundation for a vibrant, educated elite who eventually succeeded the palm oil merchants in leading the kingdom (Oko-Jaja, 2020). Interestingly, these associations midwived the emergence of other Opobo Unions across urban centers, particularly in the aftermath of Nigeria's fratricidal civil war. Among the most prominent were the Opobo Union and the Opobo Action Council. Their formation came at a pivotal moment when Opobo stood at a crossroads, grappling with the unprecedented devastation wrought by the war, the complex challenge of restoring the king to his throne in Opobo, and the contentious demand for the kingdom's merger with the newly created Rivers State (Oko-Jaja and Orji, 2019). Following the war, the kingdom faced a range of challenges, which prompted the formation of various associations aimed at mitigating or addressing these issues. Among these, the Opobo Union played a pivotal role in establishing

what could be considered the kingdom's first modern cultural club, Ere Mina Ogbo, around 1974. This initiative sparked the creation of several other similar cultural clubs within the kingdom. This study seeks to examine their contributions to the region's development from 1974 to 2024, with the goal of highlighting the significance of cultural clubs in Niger Delta communities. It further emphasizes the need for all stakeholders, especially the government, to enact laws and policies that preserve and promote these clubs, ensuring they remain strong partners in community development.

Cultural Clubs in Opobo

Opobo Kingdom is home to numerous socio-cultural clubs, but this study focuses specifically on those established with the purpose of understanding, practicing, projecting, and preserving the culture of the Ibani people for future generations. In this context, the study highlights that the first of these cultural clubs in Opobo Kingdom was the Ere Mina Ogbo, founded as the cultural arm of the Opobo Union. Its primary aim was to revive Ijo-Ibani cultural activities, especially in the areas of song and dance, which had been disrupted during the Kingdom's displacement. This disruption followed their relocation to the Eastern region, the mistaken inclusion of Opobo in South Eastern State by the federal government, their separation from their Ijo kith and kin in Rivers State, and their exile for over two and a half years due to the Civil War.

The establishment of the Ere Mina Ogbo by the Opobo Union was intended to safeguard the Opobo identity as part of the Ijo people, a development that later played a crucial role in advocating for Opobo's merger with Rivers State, a topic that will be explored further in this study. The club's membership was exclusively for Opobo women, with prominent

figures including Amaopuorubo Pighma Fubara, Madam Titi Benji Fubara, and Madam Joyce Peterside (Oko-Jaja, 2020 and Eberi Opubo Newspaper Special magazine, edition, 2021). The club became renowned for its specialization in Ekpete and Ngunume Ibani songs and dance steps, bringing both to greater prominence. Notably, there are distinct differences between the two in terms of their display patterns, with one key distinction being the number of earth pots used by the drummers. For Ekpete, seven pots are used, while Ngunume employs three, though in varying sizes, to produce sounds that harmonize with the rhythm of each song and corresponding dance movements. Another pivotal cultural organization in the Kingdom is the Ikia Mina Ogbo, founded by Amaopuorubo (Mrs.) Pauline Furo Batubo, née Cockeye Brown, in 1981. The club's primary mission was to unite young Opobo women of her age group in their collective effort to enhance and preserve Ibani culture within the Kingdom. By 1982, the movement took shape when the club was officially inaugurated with a groundbreaking event at the Port Harcourt Primary School, followed by a Dinner/Gala night at Hotel Presidential. The club's membership is exclusively comprised of Opobo women, all of whom share a deep love and commitment to the Kingdom's cultural heritage (Eberi Opubo special edition magazine, 20202).

Also, Govino Ogbo was another prominent cultural club established by Opobo women at Egwanga-Opobo, now Ikot Abasi in the early 1960s and later brought to Opobo Town. It was women club with spectacular kind of dressing like the Ibani male kind of dressing, thus, made them cynosure in the kingdom and was dominated by women of the Dappa Ye Amakiri Polo, such as, Madam Jemima Finbone, Madam Jemima Manilla, Mrs Rose Oju Fubara,

Madam Erebie Manilla, and Madam Imegwu Manilla, and they specialised in Ekpete dace aspect of the Ibani Opobo culture for years before they went moribund in the kingdom (Eberi Opubo special edition magazine, 2020 and interview with Senibo, Monday Manilla, 2025).

Further, Mina Ogbo is an other important cultural club established at Opobo in the 1970s with specialisation in Ekine cultural activities, that is renowned for its masquerade performances, which are both theatrical and sacred, embodying spirits that connect the community with the spirit in charge of their physical environment, as well as their ancestors. This club popularized the Ekine masquerade performances during the period of this study, particularly in the interregnum era in the kingdom, that the Owuogbo cultural activities was suspended. The membership of the club is open for cultural spirited sons and daughters of the kingdom with high moral standard and financial stability. In this club like in other masquerade performing organizations, the male performs the masquerade rituals and dance, while the women members of the club cheers the masquerades when performing, as well, dance round the arena when the masquerades recede for a brief rest or had finished performing. When the masquerades had finished performing and had left the arena, the women took charge of the arena, with the drummers changing their drumming pattern to rhyme with the women songs, as they dance to the rhythm of the drum, entertaining the crowd with their rich melodious voice in Ibani songs, with breath taking dangling waist.

In Opobo the Ekine masquerade groups had more of young people learning the ropes about cultural drumming and dancing, thus, prepare them to participate in the Owuogbo masquerade activities

behind the old men. The Ekine masquerade groups performed in the playground of different houses, after the Owuogbo masquerade festival. Also, Opobo culture provided the Ekine groups to perform during the “Fongu” seasons, entertaining and keeping the people reasonably happy and productive throughout the period. “Fongu” period is a time of low fishing activities in the river, thus, fishermen vacates their different fishing ports back to their main communities in the Kingdom. Oko-Jaja (2020) assert that it is a period used in appeasing the sea gods through Owu (spirit) dance ie masquerade display, and that it was a period heralded with high rainfall and sea storms, hence fishermen suspend all their activities at the sea using the period to rest and celebrate their gods.

Nonetheless, some prominent pioneer members of the Mina Ogbo are Dr. Sam Sam Jaja; Gbalolo of Opobo Kingdom, Alabo Charlse Mac pepple Jaja, Senibo Karibi Siminialayi Jaja, Senibo Benedith Siminialayi Jaja and Mrs Rose Pious Sunday Jaja (Manilla, 2025). These men and other pioneer members had rejiged the spirite of the Ekina masquerade activites in the kingdom, thus, groomed up the young ones that had succeeded them, in sustaining the objectives of the club, as well culminated in the establishment of a feeder club known as Kala Mina Ogbo and the proliferation of other Ekine cultural clubs in the kingdom.

Ibisiapu Ogbo is another important cultural club in Opobo trailing behind these other clubs. It is equally a unisex club that specialised in projecting the Ekpete Ibani songs at the kingdom, and its membership are drawn from all the sections in the kingdom. Some prominent founding members of this club are, Senibo Karibi Siminialayi Jaja, Lady Jeki Opuorubo Eunice Christopher John Jaja and Donald Michael Jaja (Manilla, 2025).

Other prominent cultural clubs at Opobo are Biri Ere Apu Ogbo, Awoibim Mina Ogbo, Ibiapu Ogbo and Opubo Bibi Mu Ere Ogbo. Pioneer founders of these clubs are distinguished personalities of the kingdom, such as Dame Christy Toby, founder of Opubo Bibi Mu Ere Ogbo and Mrs Comfort Obomanu, founder of Biri Ere Apu Ogbo (Eberi Opubo special magazine

for OWWA 50 years anniversary, 2021). Biri Ere Apu Ogbo, Awoibim Mina Ogbo and Opubo Bibi Mu Ere Ogbo are mainly female clubs while Ibiapu Ogbo is both male and female and there membership cut across the 14 sections of the kingdom, aimed at contributing to the enhancement and preservation of Ibani cultural activities, mainly in the area of songs, dance and dressing.

Govino Ogbo (Club) was in the traditional Opobo Kingdom

Source: Eberi Opubo Magazine 2021

Ikia Mina Ogbo

Source: Eberi Opubo Magazine 2021

Traditional Earth-pot Drum for Ngunume and Ekpete Dance

Source: Jaja, E. A (1977)

Lead Singer in Eremina Ogbo: Amanimibo Pighma Fubara (Oruogolo)

Source: Eberi Opubo Magazine 2021

Members of the Opobo Action Council

Source: Jaja, E. A (1977)

Contributions to the Development of Opobo Kingdom

The cultural clubs in Opobo had contributed so much in different facets to the development of the kingdom, especially in the sustaining and enhancement of Ibani

culture, as well as in human capital and infrastructural developments. On the sustenance and enhancement of the Ibani-Ijo culture at

Opobo, it is imperative to note here that, Opobo's strong participation on the palm oil trade after it's

establishment in 1870, rejiged the people intergroup relations with the Igbo hinterland, a development that affected her Ibani culture, especially language. As Andah (1988) noted, language conveys cultural meaning and seen to pervade virtually all aspects of culture. However, Opobo losing her Ibani-Ijo language to Igbo language, became a serious problem for the sustenance and enhancement of the Ibani-Ijo culture at Opobo in the post-colonial era that was besieged with modernity, thus the need for these cultural clubs that bent on reviving Ibani-Ijo language at Opobo, especially producing songs at of it for entertainment, hence, raising Opobo-Ibani-Ijo nationality. Indeed, the cultural clubs noted above performed with Ibani language, a trajectory that had given Ibani language a boost in the kingdom, thus, underscores its clamour for total revival in the kingdom as a means of communication, through the learning of the language in schools at Opobo and other learning centers in Port Harcourt, as well as production and circulation of Ibani language learning books to Opobo indigenes. The consciousness created by this development among Opobo indigenes had propelled the rise for the naming of Opobo babies with Ibani names by their parents and the production of Ibani Christian songs, as well as increasing the membership of these cultural clubs and even establishing new ones (Andrew-Jaja, 2018).

These clubs had transported Ibani culture far and near, through their songs and dance. The Ere Mina Ogbo group was the leading light in this aspect. Through their lead singer, Pighima Fubara, they produced classical Ibani songs, and some were packaged into musical albums; these songs that hit the air shortly after the civil war, helped to rekindle the hope of many Opobo people for survival of the devastation of the war, as the songs became their rallying point of

joy and happiness. Indeed, these Ibani songs, at that period raised Opobo nationality and culture into a collective asset treasured by different people, as the albums were played in different music studios in Port Harcourt, Egwaga-Opobo (now Ikot Abasi at Akwa Ibom State), Calabar and even parts of Lagos were Opobo people presence were visible (Fubara, 2018). However, it is claimed that, the musical albums produced by the Ere Mina Ogbo club were among the evidences presented before Justice Mamman Nasir Boundary Adjustment Commission by Opobo people in their argument that, Opobo is an Ijo community and has no business been in Cross River State, thus, should be merged with Rivers State where her Kith and Kin are (Fubara, 2018). Nevertheless, the packaging of the Ibani songs into musical albums, brought so much money to the club and the members, thus, made some leading members to dedicate more time and passion for the learning of Ibani language, especially composing more songs with it, hence, enhancing their talent in that area, as well as carving a niche for themselves, and this was the category Amanimibo Pighma Fubara positioned herself, thus, described as “the song bird that flew away” (Eberi Opubo special magazine for OWWA 50 years anniversary, 2021).

In essence, the achievements of Ere Mina Ogbo group on the sustenance and enhancement of Opobo-Ibani culture, in the area of language, songs and dance, attracted the admiration of younger Opobo women, thus, the proliferation of women cultural clubs at Opobo, as noted, thus joined in enhancing the rich cultural heritage of the kingdom, throughout the period of the study and even beyond. Importantly, especially, the Ikia Mina Ogbo had composed many Opobo-Ibani songs, with many packaged into musical albums, thus joined the ones of Ere Mina Ogbo in the

musical stores, where they are played, hence, popularizing the Opobo-Ibani songs and nationality in various parts of the country. Also, due to the fascinating singing and dancing patterns of these cultural clubs, they have been hired to perform in many occasions outside the kingdom, thus, propagating and showcasing the culture of Opobo-Ibani people to other parts of the world, a fact that had made people of other nationalities to develop love for Opobo kingdom, leading to their union with the kingdom through marriage or membership of one cultural group, like the Nwaotam groups, that has its membership opened to people of other nationalities (Oko-Jaja & Jaja, 2021).

The hiring of these cultural clubs to perform in an occasions within and outside the kingdom is an important milestone, as it serves as a source of revenue generation for the clubs and exposed many of the maidens in the clubs to suitors, who got them married within and outside the kingdom. However, many of them who married outside, due to their love for their culture, still retain the membership of their club and equally draw their husbands closer to the kingdom, thus contributing to the development of the area in various ways. In the same vein, the hiring of these clubs to perform in the Egerebite and Bibite ceremonies within Opobo had added glamour ad splendor to the events, thus, revolutionized the event to the admiration of almost all Opobo women, as its participation by the womenfolk had increased, hence, projecting and enhancing that aspect of culture in the face of Christianity and modernity.

Further, the activities of these clubs had also enhanced the learning of Ibani language in the area among its members. Since they compose their songs in that language, many clubs had made it mandatory that their members must understand the language,

thus, the reason for its teaching and learning in their meeting days, a fact that had contributed to increase understanding of the language among members of the cultural clubs.

The Ekine cultural clubs, in their own rights had equally contributed to the sustainability and enhancement of the Opobo-Ibani language through songs and talking drum, as well as other cultural practices through the masquerade activities. The masquerade (Owu) culture is indigenous to the Ijo people, thus, the Owuogbo society of Opobo and Ekine Sekiapu Society of Kalabari in Eastern Niger Delta (Ogolo, 2020). The Ekine Society is a strong cultural institution in Ibani kingdoms of Bonny and Opobo, as it formed the bases for the formation of the Owuogbo society.

In Opobo as noted, the two are custodians of masquerade activities, but the first stage is the Ekine which are in charge of the different houses masquerade activities and through it one graduate to the Owuogbo, which superintends the kingdom's masquerade performances.

However, within the period of the study, Christianity and modernity had affected the Ekine institution of many houses. Important fact also that affected the institution was chieftaincy vacuum in many houses, and this is because a chief control the activities of the institution in his chieftaincy house. Interestingly, the Mina Ogbo filled the vacuum of the Ekine institution in Opobo, especially in their performance during the "Fongu" periods and which ought to be the major period that the Ekine of the different houses should have performed. Indeed, the masquerade activities of the Mina

Ogbo during the "Fongu" period had helped in sustaining and projecting that cultural practices in the kingdom within the period of this study and beyond.

It is equally important to note that during the kingship interregnum 1980 to 2003, a period also that the Owuogbo activities was suspended in the kingdom, the Ekina cultural clubs sustained the masquerade performances during the festive periods that the Owugobo usually perform their masquerade activities, thereby filling the vacuum and preserving the masquerade cultural calendar of the kingdom. The activities of these Ekine clubs in the aspect of entertainment encouraged many Opobo people to keep visiting home with their families during the festive periods of the interregnum, and that contributed so much in entrenching the masquerade culture of Opobo in the minds of the younger generations that did not witness the Owuogbo masquerade performance before the interregnum period, a fact that enhanced the membership of the clubs with young cultural enthusiast and its proliferation in the area. Nevertheless, the cultural clubs as noted, inspite of sustaining and enhancing the culture of the Opobo-Ibani people, had equally involved in the human capital and infrastructural development of the Kingdom, as a way of giving back to the Kingdom, and to be an active partner in the Opobo project. Consequently, many of the clubs had engaged on charity activities in the Kingdom, through the provision of free medical services, donation of drugs and other medical facilities to health centers and hospital in the area, distribution of foods, cloths to the less privileged, as well as books to pupils and students of various schools in the area (Omubo-Pepple, 2025).

Also, clubs like Ikia Mina Ogbo had went further in their contributions, by providing scholarships to many Opobo students, as well constructed and equipped a home economics laboratory at Government Secondary School Opobo Town, a fact

the enhanced the quality of structures in the school as well, enhanced the quality of teaching and learning (Eberi Opubo special magazine for OWWA 50 years Anniversary, 2021). Interestingly, the pioneering charity activities of these clubs had snowballed in the recent time with the efforts of other social clubs in the Kingdom to the establishment of “Opobo Charity Day; a day set aside in every January for charity activities by different clubs and organizations to less privileged people in the Kingdom.

Indeed, the tapestry of the well-coordinated “Charity Day” had in no doubt contributed in alleviating poverty in the area, as the exercise comprises award of scholarship to Opobo students seeking admission into tertiary institutions, free medical services with drugs and medicated eye glasses, donation of food items, cloths, footwear, among others to less privileged people. The exercise usually held in a day in the first week of January when many sons and daughters of the Kingdom had travelled to the area for the new year celebration, thus, to enable many of them especially the less privileged to participate in the charity exercise before travelling back to their different places of work and business. In essence, to benefit from the charity exercise had become a factor that contributed why many less privileged sons and daughters visit their home during the new year festive period, thus, fostering a robust peaceful relationship and the unity of the Kingdom in general.

Challenges of the Cultural Clubs

As noted, the cultural clubs were fundamentally formed to promote and preserve the cultural heritage of their society. However, for the Opobo-Ibani people, their culture is characterized with the cosmogony of their physical environment, such as sea, rivers and creeks, that were before now crucial to their survival, and superintended by deities

characterized with benevolent and malevolent tendencies. Indeed, the need to continue enjoying the benevolence of the deities vis a vis their economic activities, underscores the propitiation of the deities through ritual cultural activities like the Ekine masquerade society. Tamuno (1999:34) highlighted more on this when he noted that “the Ekine societies masquerades symbolize the intersection between the physical and the metaphysical worlds, bringing forth the spirits of the water and ancestors to ensure the wellbeing of the community.”

Unfortunately, Christianity since its establishment in the area, in about 1864, had been a nightmare to the cultural activities of the people, thus, altering the main essence of the activities by obliterating the ritual aspects. A fact that had contributed to the syncretic tendencies witnessed between the two cultures, thus sustaining the cultural activities of the Opobo-Ibani people for merely entertainment. In a similar vein, modernity orchestrated by colonialism and sustained by its legacies are equally a serious challenge to the cultural clubs, as many youths are not interested in joining the cultural clubs, thus the limited numbers of the youth membership, posing a challenge for sustaining these clubs in future. Also, interesting factor worthy of note here is the changing school calendar system that now alienate majority of Opobo children from witnessing and participating in the cultural activities of the Kingdom as their schools resume academic activities for the new year when important cultural activities were to begin in the Kingdom during the festive periods.

Further, finance is another challenge to the cultural clubs, particularly in their contributions to human capital and infrastructural development of the areas. The major sources of finance to the clubs are their monthly membership levy and donations by

members. The amount generated through these process often time was not enough to take care of the internal needs of the clubs, thus, limiting their human capital and infrastructural contributions. Also, inadequate membership of many of the clubs had equally resulted in shortage of funds generated from levy and donations.

Conclusion

So far, this study has highlighted the significance of cultural clubs in Opobo, demonstrating their pivotal role in enhancing and preserving culture, as well as contributing to the region's human capital and infrastructural development during the study period. The cultural revival witnessed in Nigeria during the 1970s was similarly evident in Opobo, as this study has shown. Cultural revival, as defined by Kalu (2010), involves rediscovering the wisdom of our ancestors, revaluing their ceremonies, rejuvenating their names, and renewing their language. Ultimately, this study underscores that many Nigerian societies, before colonialism, possessed rich cultural values that should be revived to foster societal development and enable Nigeria to compete effectively on the global stage in the 21st century and beyond.

However, for development to be sustainable, it must be rooted in culture. Culture, in its essence, is an aggregate concept, defined by the distinctive spirit, way of life, means of living, and achievements of a people. Therefore, the cultural revival in Nigerian societies must be focused on development. In this regard, the government should collaborate with stakeholders of all nationalities to harness their culture, particularly cultural performances, for economic growth. In the case of Opobo Kingdom, efforts have already been made by the people, through cultural clubs, to promote and preserve the area's heritage. However, it is crucial for the government to

further support these cultural clubs, steering them toward creating wealth and employment opportunities for the local population and the country at large. This support would foster greater youth involvement, ensuring the continued enhancement

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and preservation of culture for future generations. Additionally, it would encourage the clubs to expand their contributions to human capital and infrastructural development.

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